

TIME4CS

SUPPORTING SUSTAINABLE INSTITUTIONAL CHANGES TO
PROMOTE CITIZEN SCIENCE IN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

D5.4: Monitoring Toolkit for RPOs

Teresa Schaefer (ZSI)

Claudia Magdalena Fabian (ZSI)

Barbara Kieslinger (ZSI)

Work Package	5
Task	5.4
Due Date	31/12/2023
Submission Date	21/12/2023
Author(s)	Teresa Schaefer (ZSI), Claudia M. Fabian (ZSI), Barbara Kieslinger (ZSI)
Reviewer(s)	Asya Salnikova (ESF), Gitte Kragh (AU)
Version	1.0
Dissemination Level	Public
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.10405577

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
0.1	16/11/2023	Deliverable outline	Teresa Schaefer (ZSI)
0.2	06/12/2023	Content for all chapters added and elaborated	Teresa Schaefer (ZSI), Claudia M. Fabian (ZSI), Barbara Kieslinger (ZSI)

0.3	12/12/2023	Document sent to internal review	Claudia Iasillo, Alessio Livio Spera (APRE), Asya Salnikova (ESF), Gitte Kragh (AU)
1.0	21/12/2023	Document finalised	Teresa Schaefer, Claudia Fabian (ZSI)

Disclaimer: The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained herein.

Table of Contents

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS.....	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
1. ABOUT THE PROJECT.....	9
2. INDICATORS FOR INSTITUTIONAL CHANGES TO SUPPORT CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT IN RPOS	10
3. TEMPLATE FOR “STOCK-TAKING” INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT FOR CITIZEN SCIENCE IN RPOS	12
3.1. GENERAL INFORMATION: OPPORTUNITIES AND BARRIERS.....	13
Opportunities	13
Concerns and barriers	13
3.2. INTERVENTION AREA: SUPPORT RESOURCES AND INFRASTRUCTURES	13
3.2.1. Strategic plans to support Citizen Science:.....	13
3.2.2. Funding Citizen Science activities:	13
3.2.3. Tools and protocols:.....	13
3.3. INTERVENTION AREA: EDUCATION AND AWARENESS.....	13
3.3.1 Internal capacity building:.....	13
3.3.2. Communication & debate:.....	13
3.3.3. Citizen Science Expertise/Governance:	13
3.4. INTERVENTION AREA: POLICY AND ASSESSMENT.....	13
3.4.1. Strategy and policy documents:	13
3.4.2. Researchers’ evaluation:.....	14
3.4.3. Management:.....	14
3.5. INTERVENTION AREA: RESEARCH.....	14
3.5.1. Citizen Science Projects/proposals/initiatives:	14
3.5.2. Publications:	14
3.5.3. Networks:.....	14
3.6. OTHER ASPECTS THAT MIGHT BE RELEVANT TO CONSIDER:	14
4. EVALUATION MODEL OF GROUNDING ACTIONS, OUTPUTS AND OUTCOMES SUPPORT INSTITUTIONAL CHANGE IN RPOS	15
5. EVALUATION AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT WORKSHOP	21
5.1 WORKSHOP AGENDA.....	22
Creating a timeline of activities:.....	22
Prioritizing activities:	22
Reflection on enablers and barriers:	22
Defining main suggestions and lessons learned:.....	22
Rating the impact on different stakeholder groups	23

Defining the main outcomes:	23
6. EVALUATION AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT INTERVIEWS	24
7. TRAINING EVALUATION	25
7.1. POTENTIAL EVALUATION ITEMS FOR TRAINING, SEMINARS, AND WORKSHOPS	25
7.2. POTENTIAL INSTRUMENTS TO COLLECT THE FEEDBACK.....	27
7.2.1 “Human Scale”.....	27
7.2.2 “Target Evaluation”	28
7.2.3 Evaluation questionnaire.....	30
7.2.4 “Hand evaluation”	30
8. CONCLUSIONS	31
ANNEX –STOCK-TAKING TEMPLATE	32

List of Abbreviations

APRE – Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
AU – Aarhus University
CC-CS – Competence Center - Citizen Science
CHX – Crowdhelix Limited
CRG – Fundacio Centre De Regulacio Genomica
DoA – Description of Action
EC - European Commission
ECSA - European Citizen Science Association
EPA - Environmental Protection Agency
ESE - Engagement & Public Education
ESF – Fondation Européenne De La Science
SFI - Science Foundation Ireland
GA – Grounding Actions
IAs - Intervention Areas
IPIC - SFI Centre for photonics, is Ireland’s centre of excellence for research, innovation and PhD training in photonics – the science and application of light
IRC - Irish Research Council
IUA - Irish University Association
KPI - Key Performance Indicator
KTU – Kaunas University of Technology
MQP - Management and Quality Plan
PI - Principal Investigator
RRI - Research & Innovation
SDG -Sustainable Development Goals

SFI - Science Foundation Ireland
RFOs - Research Funding organizations
RPOs - Research Performing organizations
T-UCC – Tyndall National Institute University College Cork
UCL – University College London
UniSR – Università Vita-Salute San Raffaele
UZH - Citizen Science Center Zurich
WP - Work Package
Y2 - Project Year 2
ZSI – Zentrum Für Soziale Innovation GmbH

Executive Summary

The current document, titled “Monitoring Toolkit for RFOs and RPOs”, has been developed within the framework of the TIME4CS project which is funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101006201.

This monitoring toolkit is based on the experiences of evaluating institutional changes to promote citizen engagement in science along the four Intervention Areas of “Research”, “Education & Awareness”, “Support Resources & Infrastructure”, and “Policy & Assessment” in four research performing organizations (RPO) - CRG, KTU, UniSR and Tyndall.

It targets representatives of RPOs who wish to trigger changes within their organizations to better support citizen engagement in research as well as to evaluate their activities and progress.

The monitoring package can be used together with the “Reflection Tool for Institutional Changes in Citizen Science”¹. While the monitoring toolkit helps to identify the current situation of institutional support for Citizen Science and monitor the progress, the Reflection Tool supports the planning phase of defining a roadmap and grounding actions that trigger institutional support for Citizen Science within RPOs.

You will find the following in this toolkit:

- A set of developed indicators that describe institutional support for citizen engagement in RPOs in the four Intervention Areas.
- A self-assessment or stock-taking template which can be used by RPOs to investigate their institutional support for Citizen Science. This stock-taking not only helps to plan grounding actions, but also supports reflecting on the changes within organizations on a regular (e.g., yearly) basis.
- An exemplary evaluation model that links activities that are implemented to support Citizen Science within RPOs, with expected/generated output and outcomes. It is a living document that should be updated on a regular basis and can be used for planning and reflection.
- A concept and detailed agenda of an evaluation workshop that can be organised yearly by members of RPOs who are responsible for implementing institutional support within their organizations and wish to collaboratively reflect on the actions taken and their outcomes so far.
- A set of interview questions for those responsible for driving change within their organizations which they can apply to colleagues who have been involved in some of the actions supporting Citizen Science in RPOs - aiming to collect broader feedback on implemented actions.
- A set of evaluation instruments that can be applied for assessing training and workshops as these are key elements in implementing institutional support for Citizen Science in RPOs.

With all these instruments we hope to provide a set of practical tools that enrich the monitoring of institutional changes supporting Citizen Science in RPOs. A detailed report on how the evaluation instruments

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6342147>

of this monitoring toolkit have been applied and what was the outcome of the evaluation and impact assessment of the TIME4CS project can be found in D5.3 Final impact assessment report².

Please note that we present the various elements of this toolkit in one concise document here. However, they can be used stand-alone or in different combinations. Thus, as a reader of this document you may come across some repetitions, such as the indicators for institutional change.

1. About the project

TIME4CS aimed to support and facilitate the implementation of sustainable Institutional Changes in Research Performing organizations (RPOs) to promote Citizen Science and public engagement (citizens and citizens associations) in science and technology.

Public engagement - in all its forms and applications, including Citizen Science - has a strong structural, transformative power at various levels of research and innovation processes. It incorporates a variety of viewpoints into problem formulation and research questions whilst taking into account moral or ethical societal concerns.

TIME4CS aimed at facilitating a way in which the scientific ecosystem could better consider societal views by supporting Research Performing organizations - i.e., research entities such as universities and research centres - in defining and implementing institutional changes that can lead to a better and more effective engagement of citizens in research and innovation. Those institutional changes inside RPOs entailed a transformation of their governance systems by considering both the social - mindset of people inside the organization – and the organizational - norms, protocols, procedures, and policy - aspects of RPOs. To facilitate this process, TIME4CS identified 4 Intervention Areas (IAs) that alone or combined stimulated the Institutional Changes necessary to promote public engagement in Research & Innovation activities:

1. Research
2. Education & Awareness
3. Support Resources & Infrastructure
4. Policy & Assessment.

For each IA, a set of Grounding Actions (GA) was defined. The GAs are to be considered as seeds to be sown, paving the way to Institutional Changes within RPOs. TIME4CS builds on the close collaboration between Front-Runners - RPOs with comprehensive expertise in Citizen Science and that have already undergone Institutional Changes - and Implementers - beneficiaries still in the early stage of the institutional adoption and/or maintenance of Citizen Science in their organizations.

The specific objectives of the project are:

- To increase knowledge on the actions leading to Institutional Changes in RPOs necessary to promote Public Engagement and Citizen Science in science and technology
- To support TIME4CS RPOs in the implementation of actions leading to Institutional Changes through continuous mutual learning and knowledge transfer programme
- To build a dynamic and inclusive Citizen Science stakeholder community

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7486205>

- To increase the awareness of the need for a sustainable and flexible organization of RPOs governance system to better respond to the evolving relationship between science and society.

2. Indicators for institutional changes to support citizen engagement in RPOs

In TIME4CS, we assumed that **both, the bottom-up institutional changes driven by the people within an organisation - and top-down approaches**, driven by changes in organisational structures - are needed.

The set of indicators to assess institutional support for Citizen Science is therefore twofold:

1. **Changes at an institutional level:** These indicators are structured along the four Intervention Areas “Education & Awareness”, “Support Resources & Infrastructures”, “Policy & Assessment”, and “Research” and are presented in the upper four rectangles in Figure 1. The indicators for changes at an institutional level are aligned with the set of indicators developed in TIME4CS through the case study analysis³.
2. **Changes at an individual level:** Indicators at this level refer to changes that researchers, students and support staff are experiencing and are presented in the bottom rectangle of Figure 1. They cannot be attributed to one specific Intervention Area only. For instance: Increases in knowledge and skills of individual participants are an expected outcome of institutional changes related to “Education & Awareness”; but can also be triggered by the implementation of a general contact point for Citizen Science, thus being related to “Support Resources & Infrastructures”. And aspects of individual change in e.g. knowledge, motivation and interest, might not only be a consequence of institutional changes but also a pre-condition to drive institutional change. In the following illustration (Figure 1) changes on the individual level are presented in the grey rectangle at the bottom.

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5807507>

Indicators for Institutional Changes to support citizen science in RPOs

Figure 1: Indicators for institutional change in TIME4CS (changes at organisational level in the blue, orange, yellow and green rectangles; changes on the individual level in the grey rectangle).

We propose to use this set of indicators to regularly reflect on institutional support for Citizen Science within RPOs. They can help to identify areas that are not well supported yet, and they can support monitoring and bringing evidence for change which is happening in organizations.

For practical usage of the indicators, we have developed a self-assessment or stock-taking template, which is presented in the next chapter.

3. Template for “Stock-taking” institutional support for Citizen Science in RPOs

The following questions serve Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) to describe the institutional support that can lead to a better and more effective engagement of citizens in research and innovation via Citizen Science. A printable version of the Stock-Taking Template can be found in the Annex of this document.

Answering these questions is a reflection exercise:

- It helps to identify areas, where more support for Citizen Science can be implemented, and demonstrate those areas, where already first institutional support for Citizen Science is already in place.
- It supports describing the baseline of institutional support before developing a roadmap of activities that aim to trigger institutional change towards Citizen Science.
- It assists in monitoring and keeping track of changes by revisiting these questions on a regular (e.g. yearly) basis.

The stock-taking questions are structured along the four Intervention Areas defined in the TIME4CS project:

1. Research
2. Education and Awareness
3. Support resources and infrastructure
4. Policy and Assessment

They contain open and closed questions, where open questions are especially important - so RPOs are invited to not necessarily get hooked on the concrete numbers. Numbers also have merit, of course, but it is also important to reflect in an open qualitative way on the current situation.

Institutions may not have the full set of support structures that are mentioned in this questionnaire in place yet. It is still recommended to keep them in and possibly reflect on them as they serve for later reference. You may want to draw a comparison with data collected after the implementation of the first activities that support Citizen Science.

Figure 1 above presents an overview of the four Intervention Areas and potential indicators in each of these areas.

3.1. General information: Opportunities and barriers

Opportunities

What do you think are the most important opportunities and triggers to make Citizen Science an accepted research approach within your organisation?

Concerns and barriers

What are the key concerns/barriers that hinder Citizen Science becoming an accepted research approach within your organisations?

3.2. Intervention Area: Support resources and infrastructures

3.2.1. Strategic plans to support Citizen Science:

- Are there any official plans in your organisation on how to support Citizen Science?
 - If yes, could you briefly describe them?

3.2.2. Funding Citizen Science activities:

- Are there funding opportunities for Citizen Science in your country?
 - If yes, could you briefly describe them?
 - Has your organisation already made use of them?
- Does your organization benefit from international/European funding of Citizen Science?
 - If yes, could you please briefly describe it?
- Is there any other internal funding available for the active involvement of citizens in research?
 - If yes, could you please briefly describe it?

3.2.3. Tools and protocols:

- Does your organisation have access to tools and technical solutions that support the implementation of Citizen Science projects (e.g. tools for data collection)?
 - If yes, could you please describe them shortly?
- Does your organisation provide legal protocols tailored to national requirements and ethical committees?
 - If yes, could you please describe them?

3.3. Intervention Area: Education and Awareness

3.4. Intervention Area: Policy and Assessment

3.4.1. Strategy and policy documents:

- Is science communication and public engagement integrated in your institutional research strategy or institutional statements?
- Does your organisation have open science policies established?
Is Citizen Science considered part of the open science policy?

- Does your organisation have any other norms, regulations and policies in place or under development that specifically refer to Citizen Science?
 - If yes, can you briefly describe them?

3.4.2. Researchers' evaluation:

- Are science communication and public engagement considered in the evaluation schemes of researchers (= academic staff appraisal)?
- Is the active involvement of citizens in scientific projects (Citizen Science) considered in the evaluation schemes of researchers (= academic staff appraisal)?

3.4.3. Management:

- Does your organisation offer presentations on Citizen Science at the management level?
- Does your organisation have any Citizen Science champions at the management level?
- Are researchers being encouraged by management to pursue Citizen Science activities?

3.5. Intervention Area: Research

3.5.1. Citizen Science Projects/proposals/initiatives:

- Are there any Citizen Science projects/proposals/initiatives in your organisation?
 - If yes, how many approximately?
 - Is there a description available of these projects to get more details on funding, disciplines, size, scope, role of citizens, etc. (e.g. a website)?
 - Are there any flagship Citizen Science projects/initiatives amongst them, e.g. with wide national/international visibility?

3.5.2. Publications:

- Are there any scientific publications related to Citizen Science within your organisation?
 - If yes, how many approximately?

3.5.3. Networks:

- Do you actively cooperate and/or network with organisations that are active in the Citizen Science field?
 - If yes, how many approximately?
 - Could you briefly describe them, please (e.g. NGOs in the environmental field ...)?
- Does your organisation have representatives in national/european-wide/international committees related to Citizen Science (e.g. ECSA board ...)?
 - If yes, could you elaborate on their engagement, please?
- Is there a national Citizen Science organisation in your country? Are you a member of it?
- Is your institution a member of the ECSA?

3.6. Other aspects that might be relevant to consider:

- Are there any other aspects that you wish to document because they influence the support for Citizen Science in your organisation?

4. Evaluation model of grounding actions, outputs and outcomes support institutional change in RPOs

After starting to implement the grounding actions, evaluation and impact assessment come into play again. Inspired by the Logic Framework Approach (LFA), we advise applying a structured process to understand the consequences of the activities planned and keep track of them regularly. With this aim, we created an evaluation model to be used by RPOs.

The planned grounding actions, involved stakeholders, expected/realized outputs and outcomes, and potential indicators to measure outputs and outcomes are collected in a table (Table 1) and regularly updated. For the planning of evaluation activities, the table could also be amended with additional data like data collection instruments, and individual stakeholder representatives who could be involved in data collection. Similarly, it could include risks and benefactory elements associated with a certain indicator.

Table 1: Implementers’ Logic Framework Approach model

Grounding action	Involved stakeholders	Expected output and outcomes	Measures/ indicators	Data collection instruments (optional)	Stakeholder representatives for data collection (opt.)

This table can be used to guide the review, discussion, and explication of grounding actions, outputs and outcomes. To show more concretely how such a model could look like, please find in the following table an evaluation model filled with exemplary content (Table 2).

Planned activities, expected outcomes and how to collect feedback from the stakeholders involved

Outputs are products or services resulting from the planned activities (e.g. workshops, participants in the workshops, etc.)

Outcomes are the effects of the outputs on the target group (e.g. a behaviour change, an increase in knowledge or skills, etc.)

Table 2: Exemplary evaluation model to support institutional changes in RPOs

Planned activities	Engaged actors	Expected outputs and outcomes	Measures/ indicators
<p>1. Planning changes in organisational structures To include Citizen Science as a pillar in the Open Science framework. To create and publish the content for the Citizen Science section as part of the Open Science web page.</p>	<p>Research support services: e.g. Communication team International and Scientific Affairs team</p> <p>Higher management</p> <p>Researchers</p>	<p>Output:</p> <p>Co-creation workshop organised</p> <p>Content for the Citizen Science section including links to all Citizen Science projects created and published</p> <p>New Citizen Science section was disseminated to the research community</p> <p>Outcome:</p>	<p>No. of co-creation workshops organised</p> <p>No. of employees involved in the co-creation of the content</p> <p>No. of resources shared in the Citizen Science section</p> <p>Dissemination activities of this new Citizen Science section</p>

Planned activities	Engaged actors	Expected outputs and outcomes	Measures/ indicators
		Increased recognition of Citizen Science as an Open Science pillar Increased visibility and awareness of Citizen Science activities	
<p>2. Raising internal awareness & training researchers on Citizen Science</p> <p>To organize an online talk describing success stories of other Citizen Science projects, explained by researchers with previous experience in running Citizen Science projects. To set up Citizen Science training programmes for PhD students and include them in the mandatory training courses for this community. To set up Citizen Science training programmes for post-docs and PIs.</p>	<p>Research support services: e.g. - Communication team - Training team</p> <p>Internal and external Citizen Science experts PhD students Post-docs PIs</p>	<p>Output:</p> <p>Content for an online inspirational talk on Citizen Science created Inspirational talks organized Course content for PhDs created Course delivered and integrated into a PhD training programme Course content for Post-docs and PIs created Course to Post-docs and PIs delivered</p> <p>Outcome:</p> <p>Increased knowledge and awareness about Citizen Science amongst researchers and students; Increased knowledge of how to plan and implement Citizen Science;</p>	<p>No. of participants in the training programmes No. of tutors engaged in the programme Hours of content delivered in the training programmes No. of participants in the inspirational talks No. of inspirational talks delivered</p> <p>Perceived usefulness of the Citizen Science course and suggestions for improvement</p> <p>Increases in knowledge and self-reported confidence to develop Citizen Science projects</p> <p>Self-reported increased interest to develop Citizen Science proposals</p>

Planned activities	Engaged actors	Expected outputs and outcomes	Measures/ indicators
		Increased interest in developing Citizen Science proposals and projects, increased confidence to do so	Self-reported uptake and practical follow up of the new knowledge by students
<p>Virtual Hub and University Contact Point for Citizen Science projects</p> <p>Organize consultation sessions about the establishment of a Citizen Science hub with higher management.</p> <p>Appointing a Contact Point for the Citizen Science projects</p> <p>Organize a discussion of the functions and the facilitation scope of the Contact Point</p> <p>Develop and adopt a feasibility study on Virtual Hub's funding and resource mobilization, accompanied by two-year activity plans.</p>	<p>Research support services: e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication team - Training team <p>Research communities from different faculties and at different levels of their career interested in implementing a Citizen Science project</p> <p>Higher management</p>	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishment of the Citizen Science Virtual Hub Appointed contact point for the Citizen Science projects Feasibility study on Virtual Hub's funding and resource mobilization <p>Outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainable support for researchers wanting to implement Citizen Science - Sustainable support for local communities, NGOs and other organizations wanting to engage in Citizen Science Increased interest and confidence in developing a Citizen Science project - Increasing the number of Citizen Science proposals and projects 	<p>No. of people involved in the definition of functions and facilitation scope as well as the establishment of the Virtual Citizen Science Hub</p> <p>Perceived usefulness of the Virtual Citizen Science Hub and suggestions for further development</p> <p>No. of researchers supported via the Contact point</p> <p>No. of proposals created with the help of the contact point</p> <p>...</p>

Planned activities	Engaged actors	Expected outputs and outcomes	Measures/ indicators
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing number of researchers involved in Citizen Science proposals and projects - Lessons learned about the establishment of the Citizen Science Hub 	
<p>3. Developing institutional guidelines on the implementation of Citizen Science projects</p> <p>To develop institutional guidelines on the principles of Citizen Science and how to design and run a Citizen Science project.</p> <p>To publish and disseminate the guidelines</p>	<p>Research support services: e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication team - International & Scientific Affairs team <p>Management</p> <p>Researchers</p>	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-creation workshops Co-developed guidelines created by support services in collaboration with scientists with and without previous experience in Citizen Science projects Guidelines describe what a Citizen Science project is, details about the process, protocols etc. They are disseminated to the researchers' community <p>Outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased knowledge and awareness about Citizen Science amongst researchers; Increased knowledge of how to plan and implement Citizen Science; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No. of co-creation workshops organised No. of employees involved in the co-creation of the guidelines Dissemination activities for the guidelines Perceived usefulness of the institutional guidelines and their applicability in different research contexts Suggestions for improvement

Planned activities	Engaged actors	Expected outputs and outcomes	Measures/ indicators
		Increased interest in developing Citizen Science proposals and projects, increased confidence to do so	
<p>4. Developing an institutional policy about Citizen Science projects</p> <p>To develop an institutional policy for Citizen Science To publish and disseminate the policy for Citizen Science.</p>	<p>Research support services: e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication team - International & Scientific Affairs team - Legal team <p>Higher management</p>	<p>Output:</p> <p>Identified gaps that are not covered by existing policies and need to be addressed Definition of types of data and engagement Co-created policy guidelines Disseminated to the researchers' community</p> <p>Outcome:</p> <p>Increased knowledge and awareness about the Citizen Science methodology from the legal, ethical and societal perspectives, about the rights and duties of the actors involved Increased interest in developing Citizen Science proposals and projects, increased confidence to do so</p>	<p>No. of co-creation workshops organised No. of employees involved in the creation of the institutional policy Dissemination activities for the policy</p> <p>Perceived usefulness of the institutional policy and its applicability in different research contexts Suggestions for improvement</p> <p>Increases in knowledge and self-reported confidence to develop Citizen Science projects</p> <p>Self-reported increased interest in developing Citizen Science proposals</p>

5. Evaluation and impact assessment workshop

In TIME4CS, we developed the concept of an evaluation and impact assessment workshop, which we applied after two years of implementing the institutional changes in RPOs that support Citizen Science. The sessions typically last about 2 hours and lead the participants through a set of collaborative reflection exercises to:

- Work on a timeline to reflect on all the activities that were organised or implemented to support Citizen Science within the organisation
- Discuss problems and solutions encountered during these activities
- Define the main outcomes of the activities
- Reflect on the impact of the activities on management, researchers, students and support staff

We suggest organising this evaluation workshop on a yearly basis to support an adaptive management of activities and to learn about the positive institutional changes that have already been implemented.

In TIME4CS, this evaluation workshop was organised online, using MiRo as the collaborative working space and here is a screenshot of how the Miro boards looked at the end of the workshop (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Example of working environment of the Final TIME4CS evaluation workshop

5.1 Workshop Agenda

In this section we will introduce the Agenda of the workshop.

Creating a timeline of activities:

Start the preparation of the workshop with the elaboration of a timeline where you list the most important grounding actions of your organisation (you can see an example of grounding actions on the left-hand side of figure 3). Then add key activities of the grounding actions (e.g. the organisation of workshops, the work on training concepts, the dissemination of a Citizen Science section, etc.)

In the workshop, ask participants to complete the timeline with important activities which are missing in the timeline. This is a very important step in creating a common understanding of all the activities which are undertaken to trigger institutional support for Citizen Science. All additions are noted down on post-its and placed on the timeline.

Prioritizing activities:

After having completed the timeline start to trigger the reflection process about the importance of different activities. Invite participants to use red and green dots to indicate:

- Which were the key or most important activities that helped to trigger change (if you don't find them in the timeline, please add them) -> green points are set next to these activities
- Which were the most difficult activities which slowed down the change process (if you don't find them in the timeline, please add them) -> red points are set next to these activities

Reflection on enablers and barriers:

From the very start of the workshop, whenever enablers and barriers of the implementation process are mentioned, note them down on post-its (you can see enablers and barriers in the example above). To get the complete picture then ask participants.

- What were enablers in the whole process (think of conditions, persons, or specific activities)
- What were the barriers in the whole process (think of conditions, persons, or specific activities)

Enablers and barriers are added on post-its.

Defining main suggestions and lessons learned:

To conclude the reflection on activities, enablers and barriers ask participants two more questions:

- What would you do differently if you had the opportunity to start the implementation of activities again?
- What are concrete suggestions for improvement from your experiences?

Again, document the input on post-its.

Rating the impact on different stakeholder groups

Then start to reflect on the impact of activities on different stakeholder groups. In TIME4CS, we suggested four important stakeholder groups: management, support services, researchers and students.

For each of these stakeholder groups, ask participants to rate the level of awareness, interest, knowledge and engagement with Citizen Science. The rating is done collaboratively - which means that all participants need to agree on the rating. This process of finding an appropriate rating helps to identify the differences of impact on different stakeholder groups and is a very interesting activity. When there are important explanations of why a certain rating is chosen, add it on post-its next to the rating.

Please find in Figure 3 a screenshot, of how these ratings were organised in the TIME4CS project:

Figure 3: Evaluation Workshop - Impact on stakeholders assessment exercise

Defining the main outcomes:

The final activity of the workshop is dedicated to the main outcomes of implementing the grounding actions so far. This exercise is perceived as summarising all that was said before, in terms of concrete outcomes. Again, this last input is added via post-its.

- What are the main outcomes of implementing the grounding actions? Please make a post-it for each outcome.

6. Evaluation and impact assessment interviews

To get the feedback of people within the RPOs who were only partly involved in the grounding actions that support institutional change in RPOs, conducting interviews can be a very interesting instrument.

Typically we would recommend 2-4 interviews within an RPO with people outside the “core teams” implementing Citizen Science at organisational level to capture a variety of opinions from other relevant stakeholders in the organisation. These could be:

- Representatives of the Management,
- Researchers who participated in trainings, workshops or expert talks
- People supporting the engagement of citizens in research, e.g. a newly appointed Citizen Science contact point or a university community officer

We suggest organising these interviews on a yearly basis, after the impact assessment workshop. In this way, the individual views on Citizen Science within RPOs can shed light on issues discussed during the workshops.

The main questions of these interviews could be:

- Could you please briefly introduce yourself?
- In which of the activities that were organised to support Citizen Science in your organisation, have you been involved so far (e.g. training, workshops, etc.)?
- How did you personally perceive these activities? What did you like and was there anything you would have longed for?
- How did the involvement in these activities or information you received about Citizen Science influence your working/research activities?
- Have you noticed an increased attention to Citizen Science in your institution overall?
- What do you personally think about Citizen Science as a research approach?
- Are you discussing about Citizen Science with colleagues?
- What do you think would be needed to further drive Citizen Science within your organisation and what should be avoided?

7. Training evaluation

The organisation of Citizen Science training and workshops for different stakeholder groups within the RPOs (support services, management, researchers) was a key activity in TIME4CS.

To learn how participants perceived the training and workshops, we developed a set of training evaluation instruments that are introduced in this final chapter of the monitoring toolkit.

7.1. Potential evaluation items for training, seminars, and workshops

In the following table we present potential indicators for the evaluation of training, seminars and workshops in the left column. The right column suggests an answering format: either **Open text** (open text field) or **Likert scale** (e.g., a 5-point likert scale from 1= completely disagree, to 5= completely agree).

Table 3: Potential indicators for training evaluation

1. Expectations and knowledge previous to the training:⁴	Answering format
What do you expect from the training on Citizen Science?	Open text
What motivates you to take part in this training?	Open text
2. Summative Questions: A selection of questions to pose after the training, seminar, or workshop	
The objectives were clear and comprehensible.	Likert scale
A good understanding of contexts was provided.	Likert scale
Practical knowledge was provided.	Likert scale
There was enough room for my questions and interests.	Likert scale
The time allotted was utilized/filled in an optimal way.	Likert scale
What did you like best?	Open text
What could be improved?	Open text
3. Immediate benefits for participants: A selection of questions to pose after the training, seminar, and workshop	
Knowledge:	

⁴ Could e.g. asked when participants register for the training or workshop

I can explain what Citizen Science is	Likert scale
I can explain why Citizen Science can be important for science and society.	Likert scale
I can outline different types of Citizen Science projects and provide practical examples.	Likert scale
I can explain the main phases of conducting a Citizen Science project.	Likert scale
<i>ETC - these questions depend on the Content of the Training, Workshop, or Seminar</i>	
Confidence:	
I feel confident that I have enough knowledge to plan a Citizen Science project	Likert scale
I feel confident that I have enough knowledge to implement a Citizen Science project	Likert scale
I feel confident in finding the right people who help me out in case I have questions related to planning and implementing a Citizen Science project.	Likert scale
I feel confident in finding good resources that support me in setting up a Citizen Science project (e.g. guidelines, tools, ...).	Likert scale
I am confident in offering the knowledge I have gained from the training to my peers.	Likert scale
Interests and attitudes:	
I am interested in following up on future Citizen Science training and activities.	Likert scale
I think that Citizen Science will be an important approach to doing science in future.	Likert scale
I think that my organisation should continue (investing in possibilities) to support Citizen Science.	Likert scale
I will suggest the training to my colleagues	Likert scale
The learning met my expectations	Likert scale
The most useful learning experience for me was	Open text
I would need further training/workshops on the following issues ⁵	Open Text

⁵ This question should only be asked, if expectations are managed, e.g. either future workshops will come

I would need the following support to get actively engaged in Citizen Science activities ⁶	Open text
4. Long-term benefits for participants: A selection of questions to pose, e.g. 8 weeks after the training, seminar, or workshop	
I have been able to apply the learning to my job/study/research	Likert scale
I actively shared the knowledge gained in the training, seminar or workshop with my colleagues	Likert scale
I feel more confident in talking about Citizen Science to others	Likert scale
I feel more confident in planning and implementing a Citizen Science project	Likert scale
I stayed in contact with other researchers interested in Citizen Science	Likert scale
I looked for further information related to Citizen Science after the training, seminar, or workshop	Likert scale
Can you share any recent experiences that have influenced your work/study/research as a result of your participation in the course?	Likert scale
I am interested in following up on future Citizen Science training and activities.	Likert scale
I would need further training/workshops on the following issues	Open text
I would need the following support to get actively engaged in Citizen Science activities	Open text

7.2. Potential instruments to collect the feedback

7.2.1 “Human Scale”

The human scale is a good instrument to trigger participants to share their opinions and collect feedback at the end of a workshop.

Participants respond to the evaluation questions by taking positions along an imaginative measurement scale on the floor of the meeting room. This exercise can lead to interesting discussions on why participants have chosen to stand in a particular spot on the scale, and what could be done differently.

⁶ This question should only be asked, if expectations are managed, e.g. further support is offered

Steps in the Human Scale:

- Imagine a straight line on the floor. Ensure the line is long enough for participants to cluster around comfortably
- Label one end of the line as “don’t agree at all” and the other end as “fully agree”.
- Ask questions that help participants to reflect on the different learning goals
- Give participants time to decide where on the scale they would like to stand in response to the question
- Once all participants have taken position on the scale, look for patterns and clusters. Choose a few participants and ask them why they chose to stand on a particular spot of the scale.

Advantages of this method:

- It triggers interesting discussion and feedback when people think about their position on the scale
- Normally participants enjoy taking part in this kind of exercise.

Disadvantages of this method:

- Participants might influence each other
- You need to carefully document what participants said

7.2.2 “Target Evaluation”

If you want an approach that is still open but less playful you could use the “Target Evaluation”:

- Draw a dart board on flip chart paper.
- Divide into 4 sections, with each section for one of the statements that need to be evaluated (see questions above).
- Ask participants to score the statements, the best being closest to the bullseye, and the worst being furthest away.
- Again, use the occasion to ask participants why they scored a certain statement closer to the bullseye or further away. Participants could also write their reflections on post-its and add them next to their score.

Here is an example of the Target that we used in one of the TIME4CS workshops (Figure 4):

Training for *Intervention Areas "Research" and "Education and Awareness"*

Please tell us, how much you agree with the following statements:

Thank you for your feedback!

Figure 4: Target evaluation of a TIME4CS Workshop

The four statements in the figure above (I can explain ..., I can evaluate ..., I would like to ..., I have a clear ...) can be adapted to the specific objectives of the workshop.

Advantages of this method:

- It triggers interesting discussion and feedback when people try to explain why they agree/disagree with a certain statement
- The rating is documented

Disadvantages of this method:

- Participants might influence each other
- You need to carefully document the discussion

7.2.3 Evaluation questionnaire

We could create a survey as the most traditional way to evaluate the workshops.

Potential questions relate to the (learning) goals of the workshops/trainings and can also be taken from section 7.1.

Advantages of this method:

- All the input is documented
- Participants do not influence each other

Disadvantages of this method:

- It is less fun and there is no collaborative reflection on the usefulness of the workshop
- You cannot trigger further discussions
- If sent out electronically afterwards, the response rate could be rather low

7.2.4 “Hand evaluation”

This is the most open format of all the formats presented so far.

- Take a flipchart and draw a big hand on it.
- Write on each of the fingers:
 - Thumb – something you enjoyed
 - Index finger – something you would like to point out (could be good or bad)
 - Middle finger – something you did not enjoy
 - Ring finger – something you will treasure from the training
 - Little finger – something little you want to add (could be good or bad)
 - Palm – a prediction for the future – what are you going to do next with this knowledge?
- Ask participants to take 6 Post-its and write their answers on the Post-its and then place them on the respective finger or their palm.
- Use the content on the Post-its to trigger discussion if you need to clarify things.

Advantages of this method:

- Input is documented
- Participants do not influence each other

Disadvantages of this method:

- It is rather open, so does not trigger any specific learning goal-oriented questions.

8. Conclusions

Institutional change means a profound change within an institution which, as a consequence, may also affect the outside environment. It may include changes in certain values and beliefs that are dominant in an institution, as well as changes in the rules, regulations and processes that lead to certain working results. In the TIME4CS project we aimed to support institutions who want to implement institutional changes towards more participatory research and Citizen Science. Implementing institutional changes that support Citizen Science in RPOs is a complex process that involves a variety of stakeholders, from top-level management to research services, researchers and students. It has strong implications on the way research is done, it challenges some disciplinary beliefs and methods, while it also needs additional support structures, regulations and protocols.

Processes of change within institutions occur continuously due to their changing environment, thus creating new demands or incentives for change. This change happens either unintentionally (thereby risking inefficiency), or in a planned and coordinated way, with executives acting as managers and coordinators. Today change management has become a professional field for internal actors, consultants and academics. However, to trigger such a complex transformation process within an RPO as an intended change towards more participatory research and Citizen Science it requires dedicated resources in terms of budget, personnel and time as well as detailed planning and regular monitoring.

This toolkit provides a set of indicators and instruments to support the planning and monitoring process for RPOs and it helps them to keep track of their institutional support for Citizen Science. It presents an initial stock-taking of institutional changes to identify areas where more institutional support is needed as a starting point for planning grounding actions. And it supports reflecting on the changes within organizations on a regular (e.g. yearly) basis via a portfolio of instruments that involve various stakeholders (management, support services, researchers and students) in the monitoring activities.

While we do not claim any exclusivity or totality in this toolkit, we see it as an inspiration for RPOs to carefully plan, reflect and assess their institutional processes in terms of supporting Citizen Science. You may come across many other useful tools and methodologies for tracking transformation. What is key to any such process, with whatever tools you may use, is the fact that it should be understood as a learning process, which needs reflection, adaptation and a certain degree of flexibility in its implementation.

ANNEX –Stock-taking template

“Stock-taking” institutional support for Citizen Science in RPOs

The following questions serve Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) to describe the institutional support that can lead to a better and more effective engagement of citizens in research and innovation via citizen science.

Answering these questions is a reflection exercise:

- It helps to identify areas, where more support for citizen science can be implemented, and demonstrate those areas, where already first institutional support for citizen science is already in place.
- It supports describing the baseline of institutional support before developing a roadmap of activities that aim to trigger institutional change towards citizen science.
- It assists in monitoring and keeping track of changes by revisiting these questions on a regular (e.g. yearly) basis.

The stock-taking questions are structured along the four intervention areas defined in the Time4CS project:

1. Research
2. Education and Awareness
3. Support resources and infrastructure
4. Policy and Assessment

They contain open and closed questions, where open questions are especially important - so RPOs are invited to not necessarily get hooked on the concrete numbers. Numbers also have merit, of course, but it is also important to reflect in an open qualitative way on the current situation.

Institutions may not have the full set of support structures that are mentioned in this questionnaire in place yet. It is still recommended to keep them in and possibly reflect on them as they serve for later reference. You may want to draw a comparison with data collected after the implementation of the first activities that support citizen science.

Here is an overview of the four intervention areas and potential indicators in each of these areas.

Indicators for Institutional Changes to support citizen science in RPOs

Figure 1: Indicators for institutional change in TIME4CS (changes at organisational level in the blue, orange, yellow and green rectangles; changes on the individual level in the grey rectangle).

General info: Opportunities and barriers

Opportunities

What do you think are the most important opportunities and triggers to make citizen science an accepted research approach within your organisation?

Concerns and barriers

What are the key concerns/barriers that hinder citizen science becoming an accepted research approach within your organisations?

1. Intervention Area: Support resources and infrastructures

1.1. Strategic plans to support CS:

- Are there any official plans in your organisation on how to support citizen science?
 - If yes, could you briefly describe them?

1.2. Funding citizen science activities:

- Are there funding opportunities for citizen science in your country?
 - If yes, could you briefly describe them?
 - Has your organisation already made use of them?
- Does your organization benefit from international/European funding of citizen science?
 - If yes, could you please briefly describe it?
- Is there any other internal funding available for the active involvement of citizens in research?
 - If yes, could you please briefly describe it?

1.3. Tools and protocols:

- Does your organisation have access to tools and technical solutions that support the implementation of citizen science projects (e.g. tools for data collection)?
 - If yes, could you please describe them shortly?
- Does your organisation provide legal protocols tailored to national requirements and ethical committees?
 - If yes, could you please describe them?

2. Intervention Area: Education and Awareness

2.1 Internal capacity building:

- How high do you think is the awareness for citizen science among your research personnel?
- And what do you think about their expertise regarding citizen science methodologies (e.g. methodologies on how to engage citizens in research, deal with data privacy aspects, and assure data quality?)
- Does your organisation offer training and teaching sessions on citizen science for researchers, support staff, students, or post-graduates?
 - If yes, how many and could you briefly describe them or provide a link to the training descriptions if available?
- Does your organisation offer workshops, inspirational talks, and informal get-togethers related to citizen science for researchers, support staff, students, or post-graduates?
 - If yes, how many approximately per year and could you briefly describe them?

2.2. Communication & debate:

- Do you have communication channels and information material, which invites the general public to be involved in research projects (e.g. a section on the institutions' website)?
 - If yes, could you briefly describe them?
- Does your organisation offer dialogue/discussions on citizen science with the general public?
 - If yes, could you briefly describe them?

2.3. Citizen Science expertise/Governance:

- Is citizen science driven by individual persons (Citizen science champions) within your organisation who are interested in citizen science?
 - If yes, how many approximately? From which research field do they come?

- Is citizen science already part of some persons' job description? And do these persons provide guidance, information, and support to other employees?
 - If yes, how many approximately?
- Is there a dedicated unit or contact point for citizen science? Does it provide support for citizen science to others inside and/or outside of the organisation? Is this unit sustainably funded or dependent on project funding?

3. Intervention Area: Policy and Assessment

3.1. Strategy and policy documents:

- Is science communication and public engagement integrated in your institutional research strategy or institutional statements?
- Does your organisation have open science policies established?
Is citizen science considered part of the open science policy?
- Does your organisation have any other norms, regulations and policies in place or under development that specifically refer to citizen science?
 - If yes, can you briefly describe them?

3.2. Researchers' evaluation:

- Are science communication and public engagement considered in the evaluation schemes of researchers (= academic staff appraisal)?
- Is the active involvement of citizens in scientific projects (citizen science) considered in the evaluation schemes of researchers (= academic staff appraisal)?

3.3. Management:

- Does your organisation offer presentations on citizen science at the management level?
- Does your organisation have any citizen science champions at the management level?
- Are researchers being encouraged by management to pursue citizen science activities?

4. Intervention Area: Research

4.1. Citizen Science Projects/proposals/initiatives:

- Are there any citizen science projects/proposals/initiatives in your organisation?
 - If yes, how many approximately?
 - Is there a description available of these projects to get more details on funding, disciplines, size, scope, role of citizens, etc. (e.g. a website)?
 - Are there any flagship citizen science projects/initiatives amongst them, e.g. with wide national/international visibility?

4.2. Publications:

- Are there any scientific publications related to citizen science within your organisation?
 - If yes, how many approximately?

4.3. Networks:

- Do you actively cooperate and/or network with organisations that are active in the citizen science field?
 - If yes, how many approximately?
 - Could you briefly describe them, please (e.g. NGOs in the environmental field ...)?
- Does your organisation have representatives in national/european-wide/international committees related to Citizen Science (e.g. ECSA board ...)?
 - If yes, could you elaborate on their engagement, please?
- Is there a national citizen science organisation in your country? Are you a member of it?
- Is your institution a member of the ECSA?

Other aspects that might be relevant to consider:

- Are there any other aspects that you want to document because they influence the support for citizen science in your organisation?